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Learning Latent Representations of Western
Classical Music Using Variational Autoencoders

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You can't blame the computer.
If there's not soul in the music, it's because nobody put it there.
And it's not the tool's fault.
— *Björk Guðmundsdóttir*

To my parents, girlfriend, friends and loved ones.

Abstract

We tackle the task of learning latent representations of Western classical music with the use of variational autoencoder (VAE) models. A large and stylistically varied corpus of polyphonic Western classical music is used for training. Musical segments are encoded as musical surface representations and several recurrent VAE models with hierarchical architectures inspired by PianoTree VAE (Wang et al. (2020b)) are trained on the data. The best model has robust reconstruction results both on seen and on unseen data, suggesting the learning of an generalisable understanding of Western music characteristics. Even though music-theory light models and music representations were used, the presence of high-level Western music theoretical concepts such as perfect fifths, major thirds or typical chord type functions are uncovered in the learnt latent representations. Semantically meaningful factors of musical variation in the latent embeddings are identified and satisfying musical interpolations are conducted, suggesting that the model possesses interesting generative capabilities. All experiments are reproducible and the code is made [publicly available](#).

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Chapter 1

Introduction

There is a strong academic interest in getting a better understanding of *music*, and especially of *Western classical music*, henceforth referred to as *Western music*. To that end, there has historically been constant and various efforts to *model* Western music, that is, to represent it in an conceptual way that makes use of informative abstractions to help its understanding by humans. From these efforts stem generally accepted conventions of *Western music theory*; those include the use of the chromatic scale, the use of Western musical notation which regulates the visual representation of melodies and rhythm, and the use of high-level musical abstractions that go beyond note pitches and durations, such as chords, keys or musical form.

In the past few decades, the application of computational techniques and data-driven approaches to the topic of music modelling has brought about new ways of understanding music. Those methods allow to learn from music directly, with little to no use of explicit predefined rules or concepts. Then, resulting implicit structures discovered to underlie musical compositions can be compared to well-established paradigms of Western music theory, thereby fostering a deeper understanding of Western music's inherent characteristics.

A data-driven approach for music modelling that has seen considerable traction in the past few years is the use of AI generative models. By their use of latent variables, these models allow to link the directly observable surface of music pieces to latent information about music that is not directly observable, such as keys and chords. These models have then proved to be very useful for the investigation of higher-level abstractions of music in recent literature.

Such generative models can be more or less music-theory heavy in structure; music-theory heavy models are ones that make considerable use of existing music-theoretical concepts, such as chords, chord types or keys, in their model structure. Those models are designed to answer specific questions from a certain pre-established music-theoretical perspective. Contrastingly, music-theory light models rely on more generic and domain-independent principles that make less use of such assumptions and concepts. Therefore, they can be said to be more agnostic to music theory to a certain extent, which enables the analysis of music with fewer theoretical preconceptions. This allows the discovery of new phenomena not usually explored in music theory at the potential cost of being slightly less interpretable with respect to pre-established musical conceptions.

Similarly, the music data used by such models must be encoded according to *music repre-*

sentations that can also be more or less music-theory heavy; the more higher-level abstractions are added to the representation (chords, keys, etc.), the more it becomes interpretative and reliant on certain pre-established theoretical concepts. Again, using data that makes little use of such musical preconceptions can bring about interesting new insights about the characteristics of music.

In this thesis, we wish to delve into the application of music-theory light models and data to data-driven modelling techniques introduced beforehand. By doing so, we aim to obtain latent representations that encode Western music’s characteristics in a way that is as informative and generalizable as possible, without the imposition of strong rules or supervision on the model that would stem from pre-established Western music theory concepts. We then aim to analyse and interpret these learnt latent representations and to compare them with pre-existing concepts of Western music theory.

For the purpose of this task, we propose the use of the *auto-encoding variational Bayes* (AEVB) to discover musical surface structure latent representations and learn from them. More particularly, we propose the use of *variational autoencoders* (Kingma and Welling (2013)), henceforth referred to as VAEs. VAE models have long proved their efficacy at producing meaningful latent representations for natural data; they also have seen pertinent applications in the music literature already, making them well-suited for the task at hand. In order to learn as generally as possible about Western music, VAE models are trained on a large, polyphonic and stylistically varied Western music corpus compiled by the Digital and Cognitive Musicology Lab (DCML) at EPFL. The corpus contains a large collection of annotated music scores ranging from the 17th to the 20th century.

In short, we desire to use VAE models to discover latent representations of musical surface structure in a theory-light manner and to find meaningful musical interpretations of these latent representations. We go beyond existing VAE approaches in music modelling by training on a larger and more complicated musical corpus and by keeping as a main goal the analysis of resulting latent spaces and their comparison to pre-established musical theory concepts.

In Chapter 2, a literature review is conducted and past efforts in the use of various music representations are explored. An investigation of music modelling is also conducted, with a strong focus on VAE models; learnings are drawn from their past applications in sequence prediction and music modelling tasks.

In Chapter 3, our methodology is explained. The dataset is described, as are the data preprocessing and augmentation pipelines; summary statistics are also provided for the final data. Results from preliminary experiments are also presented, and the proposed model architecture and training scheme are described.

In Chapter 4, the results stemming from our experiments are discussed. The reconstruction performance of the models is first explored. Then, various levels of latent embeddings learnt by the models (note embeddings, chord embeddings and final latent embeddings) are analysed, and the presence of high-level Western music theoretical concepts is uncovered. The model’s generative capabilities is also explored via musical interpolation experiments.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

Music is not an easily defined concept as its manifestations vary immensely across cultures; however, in the context of Western music, which this thesis will focus on, it can be defined as "the art of combining vocal or instrumental sounds (or both) to produce beauty of form, harmony, and expression of emotion" (Allen (1992)).

A widespread fascination for music, coupled with it being such an abstract concept, has led to a constant historical interest into ways of *modelling* it, that is, of representing it in a conceptual way that makes use of informative abstractions to help its understanding by humans. To model music effectively, one must then make a wise choice of *music representation*; as mentioned beforehand, this representation can be more or less music-theory heavy in structure. The use of a certain representation necessarily induces numerous biases in downstream tasks by attaching more-or-less preconceived assumptions about the way music should be represented, making the choice of an appropriate one of the utmost importance; in section 2.1, types of music representation that have seen the most use in the music modelling literature will therefore be investigated.

Once a music representation has been chosen, one must also choose a model; once again, this model can be more or less music-theory heavy in structure. An immensity of model types and classes have been proposed for music modelling tasks. Even in the specific field of unsupervised inference models used for musical tasks, types of probabilistic models abound: for example, Hidden Markov Models (White and Quinn (2018)), Dirichlet models (Harasim et al. (2021), Moss and Rohrmeier (2021)), probabilistic abstract context-free grammars (Harasim (2020)) and specialized variational inference models (Finkensiep et al. (submitted)) have all seen some use in the literature. However, our review will be focused on VAEs; in section 2.2, they are extensively investigated, as well as their applications, especially in the field of music modelling.

2.1 Music Representations

2.1.1 Audio Representations

Music, while being a cognitive phenomenon, is often associated to the most common cause of its manifestation, which is through sound, or vibration of air (Finkensiep (2023)). A natural way to represent music is then simply as a series of raw audio waves, resulting in so-called *audio representations*. Those representations, which are characterized by a

low amount of higher-level musical abstractions, have been historically hard to work with in the field of music modelling. However, the introduction of WaveNet (van den Oord et al. (2016)), a deep learning model that successfully handles raw audio data, has recently stimulated such approaches. Coupled with the use of attention mechanisms, as introduced by Vaswani et al. (2017), recent research has resulted in numerous impressive models that make use of raw audio representations, such as Jukebox (Dhariwal et al. (2020)), DDSF (Engel et al. (2020)) or MusicLM (Agostinelli et al. (2023)).

2.1.2 Representations Stemming from Western Music Theory

Music specialists in the Western world have developed formulations to structure Western music's observable phenomena. This process resulted in *Western music theory*, which introduces concepts such as the use of the chromatic scale, which separates an octave in a set of twelve discrete pitches, and Western musical notation, which regulates the visual representation of melodies and rhythms. The resulting categorisation of note pitches and durations into discrete possibilities allows for new interpretations of musical notes and representations of music.

The first interpretation consists of seeing notes as tokens. Following this idea, music can be represented as a series of tokens, resulting in *token-based representations*. There is theoretically no limit to the amount of musical information that can be contained in the tokens, resulting many such approaches. For example, Music Transformer (Huang et al. (2018)) models music as a series of "note on", "note off" and "time shift" tokens; expanding on this representation, Oore et al. (2018) add velocity to the tokens, and MMM (Ens and Pasquier (2020)) add MIDI instrument and track information. The use of such token representations has seen some traction with the recent rise of attention-based models, resulting in large-scale models such as MuseNet.

In the second interpretation, music can be represented as a two-dimensional array, of which the first dimension represents time (with increments defined by a quantisation grid), and of which the second dimension represents the pitches that are being played at that time (encoded as a multi-hot vector). These are called *piano-roll representations*. Due to the easiness of handling such data, these representations are vastly popular in the music modelling literature, with notably the application of influential VAE approaches such as that of Roberts et al. (2019) or Brunner et al. (2018), which will be further discussed in 2.2.4.

There also exists representations that combine aspects of both piano-roll and token-based representations. For example, Wang et al. (2020b) represent musical data as an array where the first dimension is time, but where each slice of this array contains notes encoded as tokens with pitch and duration information.

A common trait of the representations mentioned so far is that they solely use *musical surface* structure, which consists of the observable lowest-level abstractions of music that result from Western music theory, namely note pitches and durations. There has also been considerable work in the literature with music representations that use higher-level abstractions such as chords (e.g. Madjiheurem et al. (2016)) or ornamentation patterns (e.g. Finkensiep et al. (submitted)).

2.2 Variational Autoencoders (VAEs)

2.2.1 Model and Applications

Generative modelling is an approach that aims to estimate the underlying probability distribution $p(x)$ of some data, given a set of examples $x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_x}$. A lot of those approaches introduce the use of *latent variables* that define a lower-dimensional space $z \in \mathbb{R}^{d_z}$, where $d_z \ll d_x$, from which data points x are generated through a distribution $p(x|z)$. The goal of using latent variables is to tentatively explain the structure of high-dimensional complex data x with a higher-level representation z that encodes the main characteristics of the data and facilitates representation learning. Then, generative models try to find $p(x)$ by marginalising z from the joint probability $p(x, z)$. However, for most models, the integral that needs to be computed for this marginalisation process is intractable.

To solve this problem, recent advances in generative modelling have suggested the use of a technique called *variational inference* to estimate an approximate distribution for $p(z|x)$. This technique consists of choosing the distribution within a family \mathcal{Q} of approximate distributions that is the best possible approximation for the exact distribution $p(z|x)$. In practice, this best possible approximation is found by determining the distribution $q \in \mathcal{Q}$ that minimises the Kullback-Leibler divergence (KL-divergence) from the true unknown distribution:

$$q^*(z|x) = \arg \min_{q(z|x) \in \mathcal{Q}} D_{KL}(q(z|x)||p(z|x)).$$

As developed in [Kingma and Welling \(2013\)](#), this minimisation problem is equivalent to the maximisation of this term known as the *evidence lower bound* (ELBO), which can then serve as a training objective to find q^* :

$$ELBO = E_z [\log p(x|z)] - D_{KL}(q(z|x)||p(z)).$$

Developing on this idea, the same authors propose the *auto-encoding variational Bayes* (AEVB) approach, which consists of introducing variational parameters ϕ and generative parameters θ to respectively approximate the latent and the generative distributions:

$$ELBO_{AEVB} = E_{z \sim q_\phi(\cdot|x)} [\log p_\theta(x|z)] - D_{KL}(q_\phi(z|x)||p_\theta(z)).$$

This general approach allows the use of any possible parametric distributions for p and q . However, a specific model stemming from the AEVB approach, introduced by the authors in the same paper, has proved to be especially useful and popular; this model is called the *variational autoencoder* (VAE). In this type of model, an isotropic multivariate Gaussian is used as the prior distribution $p(z)$, which then lacks parameters θ ; additionally, θ and ϕ are the parameters of two artificial neural networks that approximate $p_\theta(x|z)$ and $q_\phi(z|x)$ respectively. The model architecture then consists of an *encoder network* $q_\phi(z|x)$, which encodes data points x in the latent space z , and a *decoder network* $p_\theta(x|z)$, which decodes points from the latent space z and generates data points x . The final VAE training objective is then as follows:

$$ELBO_{VAE} = E_{z \sim q_\phi(\cdot|x)} [\log p_\theta(x|z)] - D_{KL}(q_\phi(z|x)||p(z)).$$

This training objective benefits from being interpretable. The first term represents reconstruction loss (the average log-probability of data points x decoded from their encoded latent embeddings z) and the second term acts as a penalty or regularisation term on the gaussianity of the latent space (divergence between the distribution of the learnt latent embeddings and an isotropic Gaussian). Maximising the ELBO then becomes a matter of trade-off between reconstruction quality (which favours a non-smooth, very structured latent space) and gaussianity or smoothness of the latent space (which favours an uninformative distribution for z); a good VAE model then learns to encode data in a smooth latent space in a way that is still informative, bringing about generative capabilities by means of decoding interpolated or random points from z . In practice, both terms in the training objective are empirically estimated as averages over a set of *training observations*; a gradient-descent-based algorithm is then applied on the training objective function and the parameters of the encoder and decoder neural networks are updated until convergence.

VAE models offer multiple advantages. Their structure makes use of artificial neural networks, which have been shown to possess considerable expressive power (Hornik et al. (1989)). If trained properly, they have powerful representation learning properties and effectively encode high-dimensional data x within a compact latent space z whose shape should resemble an isotropic Gaussian, which is a simple and interpretable distribution. This compact representation can then be interpreted to try to understand the underlying structure of the data, which can provide interesting representation learning insights, such as the discovery of attribute vectors which represent complicated data characteristics (e.g. having blonde hair) in a low-dimensional vector encoding. These insights can allow for better understanding of inherent factors of variation in complicated data, provide new tools for reasoning and stimulate creativity, as explored by Carter and Nielsen (2017).

VAEs also allow the generation of new data points by supplying points z to the decoder network $p_{\theta}(x|z)$, which are easily sampled due to the approximate Gaussian nature of z . If a VAE is properly trained, it is then common to make use of random points sampled from z to generate realistic and expressive new data points that make use of the model's understanding of the structural properties of the original data. Research has also seen a widespread use of interpolation techniques, which consist in decoding points along a trajectory between two latent embeddings in the latent space z ; spherical interpolation tends to be used more often as it results in more realistic generation of new data points than linear interpolation techniques due to the imposed gaussianity of the latent space (White (2016)). VAEs can also be trained efficiently using recent advances made in the training of artificial neural networks. Finally, their structure allows the use of any possible artificial neural network architecture, which enables handling various types of data, such as images, text or videos.

As a consequence, since they were first proposed by Kingma and Welling (2013), VAEs have seen a widespread use in creative applications of deep learning, such as image generation (Gregor et al. (2015)), sentence interpolation (Bowman et al. (2016)) or various musical applications (see 2.2.4).

2.2.2 Recurrent VAEs

As mentioned in 2.2.1, VAEs allow the use of any possible artificial neural network architecture for the encoder and decoder networks. Thus, when working with sequential data, a natural choice of architecture is *recurrent neural networks* (RNNs), an extension of neural networks that allows to process sequences of inputs, as first proposed by Rumelhart and

McClelland (1987). VAEs that make use of such models within their architecture are called *recurrent VAEs*.

However, vanilla RNN models are known to suffer from exploding and vanishing gradient problems, which strongly impede their training and capability of learning long-term dependencies (Bengio et al. (1994)). It is then common to use more expressive RNN architectures such as *Long-Short Term Memory* (LSTM), introduced by Hochreiter and Schmidhuber (1997), or *Gated Recurrent Unit* (GRU), introduced by Cho et al. (2014). Another common problem with vanilla recurrent models is the tendency of prediction errors to accumulate: to counter this, it is common to use *scheduled sampling* as first introduced by Bengio et al. (2015). At each decoding step during training, a *teacher forcing rate* defines the probability of using the ground truth token as the next input for the decoder instead of the predicted one, forcing the model to learn from its expected prediction. This rate is usually initialized at a high value and slowly decays as training goes on so that the model can slowly learn to perform inference on its own.

Even with all these strategies, first applications of recurrent VAEs, such as that of Bowman et al. (2016), identify a significant challenge to the training of such models. They observe that since recurrent models such as LSTMs already possess strong expressive power, and since the latent space z is uninformative and noisy in early stages of training, the LSTM decoder in a recurrent VAE starts to ignore the latent space embeddings and starts modelling the data on its own. The training process then slowly ends up setting the encoder model $q_\phi(z|x)$ equal to the uninformative prior $p(z)$ so that the KL-divergence cost in the ELBO objective falls to zero; as the posterior distribution collapses to the prior, this is known as the *posterior collapse problem*. This results in a completely uninformative latent space that is unused by the model, and an inefficient training scheme for a simple LSTM model. Various strategies have been proposed to limit the noxious effects of posterior collapse: Bowman et al. (2016) propose annealing the KL-divergence cost as the training process advances or artificially weakening the decoder with token dropout such that it needs to rely more on the latent embeddings, and Roberts et al. (2018) suggest the use of a hierarchical model that makes continuous use of the latent embeddings as the decoding process goes on.

2.2.3 VAE Latent Space Interpretability

There is strong interest in *interpreting* the latent space of VAEs; that is, of analysing them in a way that provides an understanding of their general structure and that allows to semantically interpret its dimensions in a meaningful way. If the latter is possible, it opens a lot of doors for *controllable generation*; that is, for being able to generate new datasets in a controllable way according to well-defined desired characteristics. For example, controllable music generation would allow one to generate music that has desired properties for melody, rhythm or musical style. As real-world applications of generative modelling often revolve around the use of controllable generation, there is a considerable amount of past research in interpreting VAE latent spaces.

A common impediment to latent space interpretability that has been widely observed in the literature is a phenomenon called *entanglement*. A latent space is entangled when the meaningful semantic factors of variation of the underlying data x are tangled across the latent space dimensions, instead of each being associated to a very small number of latent dimensions. As it becomes an arduous task to identify the semantic factors of variation from the latent space alone, this phenomenon strongly impedes the interpretability of the

latent space and controllable generation possibilities. A large array of strategies has then been proposed to *disentangle* latent space dimensions and make the VAE latent space more interpretable and controllable, both under unsupervised and supervised paradigms. Perhaps the most popular unsupervised method is the use of β -VAEs, as first suggested by Higgins et al. (2017). The authors suggest the addition of a β coefficient in the training objective of the VAE:

$$ELBO_{\beta\text{-VAE}} = E_{z \sim q_{\phi}(\cdot|x)} \left[\log p_{\theta}(x|z) \right] - \beta \cdot D_{KL} \left(q_{\phi}(z|x) || p(z) \right).$$

This coefficient can be interpreted as a weight allocated to the penalty term, which is the Kullback–Leibler divergence between the prior distribution of the latent space and its learnt posterior distribution as modelled by the encoder network. By increasing the value of β , a higher penalty is allocated to this term, forcing the model to encode a latent space that is closer to that of the prior distribution. If that prior distribution is an isotropic Gaussian, this puts an implicit independence pressure on the learnt latent space, hopefully resulting in latent space dimensions that are less correlated and therefore more easily interpretable.

Since their introduction, β -VAEs have been extensively used for various applications due to their practicality and possible use without prior knowledge about the latent space structure due to their unsupervised nature. However, this increased disentanglement ability in β -VAEs comes at the expense of reconstruction quality, as symbolized by the first term of the training objective now having a lower relative weight than for normal VAEs. This phenomenon, often nicknamed the "reconstruction-disentanglement trade-off", was formally proved by Sikka et al. (2019) and puts an inherent limit to the amount of uncorrelation that can be forced upon the model while still achieving desirable levels of downstream performance.

β -VAEs have inspired a myriad of other extensions to VAEs that aim to disentangle the latent space in an unsupervised way; to name a few, AnnealedVAE (Burgess et al. (2018)), FactorVAE (Kim and Mnih (2019)), β -TCVAE (Chen et al. (2019)), Wasserstein autoencoders (Rubenstein et al. (2018)) and DIP-VAE (Kumar et al. (2018)). However, the general ability of those unsupervised methods to recover semantically meaningful factors of variation in the form of disentangled latent space dimensions has been put into question by Locatello et al. (2019). In a systematic study, they show that those training schemes and their corresponding losses successfully encourage certain properties on the latent space, but that this obligatorily induces biases on the model and that the use of those constrained representations does not decrease the sample complexity of downstream learning tasks.

An array of supervised schemes has also been proposed to disentangle VAE latent spaces. However, those methods require a level of prior knowledge about desired properties of the learned latent space so that they can be enforced in a supervised way; this inherently gives rise to inductive biases in the resulting models. Examples of such methods are I-VAE (Adel et al. (2018)), S2-VAE (Locatello et al. (2020)), AR-VAE (Pati and Lerch (2021a)), GLSR-VAE (Hadjeres et al. (2017)), CVAE (Sohn et al. (2015)) and EC²-VAE (Yang et al. (2019b)). However, systematic studies as such that conducted by Pati and Lerch (2021b) have suggested that even though such supervised methods can train a strong discriminative encoder, the resulting disentangled latent space does not guarantee better controllability of the disentangled attributes, once again casting shadow on the possible panacean properties of existing disentanglement methods.

2.2.4 Use of VAEs for Music Modelling

As mentioned beforehand, music modelling is a topic that has seen countless applications of VAE models. Indeed, their inherent compact latent space allows for an interesting analysis of musical properties and factors of variations in music, resulting in feature learning capabilities that can be useful for downstream tasks. Furthermore, if the latent space proves to be strongly disentangled and interpretable, this opens the door to controllable generation of music and a myriad of creative possibilities. It then comes as no surprise that they have been used for a wide range of musical applications with various types of music encodings, such as modelling timbre spaces (Esling et al. (2018)), modelling expressive piano performances (Jeong et al. (2019)), generating interactive music palettes (Roberts et al. (2018)) or generating music by analogy (Yang et al. (2019b)).

Perhaps the most influential VAE model architecture for music is MusicVAE, proposed by Roberts et al. (2019). The authors model music as a sequence of tokens (pitches) in time, where each time step is a sixteenth note. They then train a recurrent VAE model on both "short" (two bars) and "long" (eight bars) musical sequences in common time from a large corpus of publicly-available MIDI files. This model uses a bidirectional LSTM encoder to map sequences to the latent space, and a hierarchical unidirectional LSTM decoder to reconstruct the sequences; the hierarchical nature of the decoder is found to increase the dependence of the decoder on the latent code and to effectively mitigate posterior collapse problems. The resulting model is found to have strong reconstruction performance, as well as useful sampling and interpolation capabilities. However, a strong limitation of MusicVAE is that it is inherently limited to monophonic music, as its recurrent structure is formulated so that it outputs one note prediction per time step.

A polyphonic extension to MusicVAE was thus proposed by Wang et al. (2020b) in the form of PianoTree VAE. Just like MusicVAE, the authors model music as a sequence in time; however, they consider element of this sequence to be itself a sequence of tokens (pitches), limited to a maximum number K . This approach then successfully allows the modelling of polyphonic music by allowing the output of multiple pitches in a same time step. The authors also use GRUs instead of LSTMs, as the former were shown to have comparable performances to the latter for polyphonic music modelling while being faster to train due to a smaller number of parameters (Chung et al. (2014)). Similarly to MusicVAE, the resulting PianoTree VAE model also shows great reconstruction, sampling and interpolation results for polyphonic music after being trained on the POP909 dataset (Wang et al. (2020a)), a MIDI collection of polyphonic Chinese pop music. Other polyphonic extensions to MusicVAE were also proposed by e.g. Hennig et al. (2017), Brunner et al. (2018) or Tan and Herremans (2020).

There has also been some interest in the literature for the interpretability of latent spaces learned by VAE models trained on music data, as the understanding of the latent space's structure makes for more easily controllable music generation. Some authors use disentanglement techniques to constrain the model to learn a latent space that is more easily interpretable. As unsupervised disentanglement methods were mostly found to be ill-suited for music-based tasks (Pati et al. (2020)), more focus has been put on the use of supervised disentanglement techniques. For example, Yang et al. (2019b) force a subset of the latent space to encode rhythm representation by adding an intermediate rhythm reconstruction loss term to the objective function, and Tan and Herremans (2020) use AR-VAEs to regularise given dimensions of the latent space with respect to continuous-valued musical attributes.

Alternatively, some authors focus on interpreting and understanding the latent space representations learned by an unconstrained model; for example, [Yang et al. \(2019a\)](#) identify and isolate pitch and rhythm representations within the latent space learned by a MusicVAE model by observing the variation between encodings of pitch-augmented and rhythm-augmented data and show that the use of these dimensions allow controllable music generation. Some authors also use dimensionality reduction techniques such as principal component analysis (PCA) ([Pearson \(1901\)](#)) or t-distributed stochastic neighbour embeddings (t-SNE) ([Maaten and Hinton \(2008\)](#)) to reduce the dimensionality of the latent spaces learned by various models to two or three dimensions to facilitate their interpretation and understanding, as done by [Wang et al. \(2020b\)](#) or [MuseNet](#).

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1 Data

3.1.1 Dataset Used

For the dataset, the entirety of the publicly published **DCML corpora** are used; these include twelve corpora of Western music from the common practice period ranging from the 17th to the 20th century. The compilation of those corpora is part of the **Corpus Project**, an ongoing initiative of the DCML that aims to create a "large corpus of music with expert annotations of tonal harmony, counterpoint, and musical form, using newly developed annotation standards". The twelve corpora in question are listed below, grouped by reference paper:

- "*The Annotated Beethoven Corpus (ABC)*" ([Neuwirth et al. \(2018\)](#))
- "*The Annotated Mozart Sonatas*" ([Hentschel et al. \(2021b\)](#))
- "*Arcangelo Corelli - Trio Sonatas*" ([Hentschel et al. \(2021a\)](#))
- "*Ludwig van Beethoven - Piano Sonatas*", "*Frédéric Chopin - Mazurkas*", "*Claude Debussy - Suite Bergamasque*", "*Antonín Dvořák - Silhouettes*", "*Edvard Grieg - Lyric Pieces*", "*Nikolai Medtner - Tales*", "*Robert Schumann - Kinderszenen*", "*Pyotr Tchaikovsky - The Seasons*" and "*Franz Liszt - Années de Pèlerinage*" ([Hentschel et al. \(2022\)](#))

The dataset consists of *annotated music scores*. They therefore contain all the basic elements of musical surface structure that are present on music scores, such as note and rhythm information, but they are also annotated for higher-level musical abstractions such as chords labels, following the DCML standards for harmonic annotations as described in [Neuwirth et al. \(2018\)](#).

Because of the large size of the dataset and because of the wide range that it covers both across musical periods and musical styles within the common practice period of Western music, the dataset is found to be extremely well adjusted for the goals of training a VAE model that encodes Western music in a general way and of interpreting and learning from its resulting latent space.

3.1.2 Proposed Music Representation

Our main goal is to learn a VAE latent space that encodes Western music in an informative way and to compare this resulting latent space with pre-existing concepts of Western music theory. This guides the choice of music representation towards one that, while stemming from Western music theory, only contains some of its lower-level musical abstractions such as the use of the chromatic scale and Western music notation concepts of note pitches and durations. This choice of representation will softly guide the model to "learn" Western music theory in a theory-light manner, only observing the *musical surface structure* of Western music, allowing for an interesting investigation of how higher-level musical abstractions manifest themselves in the model. Naturally, this suggests the use of one of the *musical surface* representations stemming from Western music theory explored in 2.1.2. Furthermore, the data is available in the form of annotated music scores, allowing for an easy transposition to musical surface representations. Additionally, the musical surface representation needs to support the polyphonic nature of the dataset. We therefore opt for the data representation proposed by Wang et al. (2020b), which is described below.

Musical segments are encoded as sequences in a hybrid form between piano-roll and token-based approaches, as introduced in 2.1.2. Since music is encoded as sequences, the first dimension of the data representation is time. Each of the time slices of the representation contains all the information about the notes who are played at that time, that is, that have an onset equal to the considered time slice. Time slices are allowed to contain up to fourteen notes played at the same time, effectively allowing for polyphonic music. As for individual notes, they are encoded as a concatenation of two vectors:

- Pitch of the note, one-hot encoded as a 131-dimensional vector; one for each of the 128 possible MIDI pitches stemming from Western music theory, one for beginning of sequence, one for end of sequence and one for padding.
- Duration of the note in time slice units, binary encoded; due to the binary encoding, the size of the duration vector varies according to the longest possible note duration that will be supported by the model.

In terms of notation, as per Wang et al. (2020b), a musical segment is referred to as a *score*, and time slices of a score are named *simunotes*. For the time slice unit, we decide to use sixteenth notes, as used by Roberts et al. (2019) and Wang et al. (2020b). The proposed data representation is illustrated in Figure 3.1.

We propose the use of single bars (measures) of music as the score unit; that is, we wish for each bar in the dataset to be encoded as one observation. This use of bars as musical segments is motivated by several reasons. First, the limited capacity of recurrent VAE models does not allow for a successful encoding of very long sequences, as shown by Bowman et al. (2016). Encoding entire music pieces as observations is thus unachievable, and pieces need to be split in shorter units. The most natural way to split Western music pieces is in terms of bars, which are the building blocks of a music piece.

Second, successful recurrent VAE for music models in the literature have also focused on short segments of music where observations consist of one, two, four or eight consecutive bars of music (Roberts et al. (2019), Brunner et al. (2018), Wang et al. (2020b)). As for the chosen musical segment length of one bar, this is explained by our belief that the musical structure of the music in our dataset is more complicated than that of the music used by the aforementioned existing approaches. For example, Roberts et al. (2019) use

Figure 3.1: Illustration of the proposed music representation in the case of a common time observation. Here, quarter notes are used as the time slice unit, but the proposed representation uses sixteenth notes. Figure borrowed from Wang et al. (2020b).

monophonic music, and Wang et al. (2020b) train their model on a corpus of Chinese pop music; as for our dataset, it is of highly polyphonic nature, and is composed of classical music which is generally much more structurally complex than pop music. The dataset also has high stylistic variation compared to previous approaches, as it contains both mono- and poly-instrumental music, as well as a variety of musical styles such as e.g. mazurkas, piano sonatas, trio sonatas or string quartets. These characteristics will complicate the task of learning musical structure for the models compared to previous approaches; we therefore decide to stay on the safe side in terms of musical segment length to simplify the models’ learning processes, and single bars are chosen as the score unit.

3.1.3 Data Preprocessing

As the data contained in the dataset described in 3.1.1 is not already encoded in the music representation form proposed in 3.1.2, a data preprocessing pipeline must be built to encode the data as such and allow it to be used to train models. The used data preprocessing process is quickly described below; more specific implementation details can be seen in the publicly available code.

For each piece of music in the dataset, the associated **notes.tsv** file, which contains all notes information about the music piece, is used. For each bar of music, all the notes that have their onset in that bar are looked at. The bar data is then went through a sequential motion according to the time slice unit (sixteenth notes); for each sixteenth note slice, the pitch and duration of each note with this onset at the corresponding location of the multi-dimensional array described in 3.1.2 are encoded. For tied notes, their duration is simply added to the duration of the note they are tied to, unless they are at the start of a bar.

This preprocessing pipeline has its share of induced approximation errors, which are listed below and justified if appropriate:

- Since use discrete increments of sixteenth notes are used as the time slice unit, this requires *quantisation* of the notes, both for their onset and for their duration:
 - Onset: the onset of notes that are in-between two time slice units is rounded down to the previous time slice unit.

- Duration: the duration of notes that do not last a discrete amount of time slices are rounded down, or rounded up if their duration is between zero and one time slices. This is required because of the binary encoding of the note duration vector requiring a discrete number of time slice units.
- In the dataset, the resulting approximations are mostly on triple notes and on thirty-second notes, which have relatively rare occurrences in the data.
- As the notes information in **notes.tsv** files is used, the model completely ignores empty bars, which are therefore not in the resulting dataset. We deem this approximation justified, as empty bars do not contain any form of musical surface structure and would not contribute to the learning of music.
- If multiple notes have the same pitch and the same onset, they will all be combined into one single note in the preprocessed observation. This is because the one-hot encoding of pitch only allows the presence of one note per pitch per time slice. This causes approximation errors if there is, for example, two instruments playing the same note at the same time, or two thirty-second notes of the same pitch quantised to the same onset. However, due to the rare occurrence of those cases, we deem this approximation justified.
- Grace notes are ignored, as they are given a duration of zero in **notes.tsv** files. We believe this approximation acceptable due to grace notes of being melodically and harmonically nonessential by nature.
- Pick-up bars are ignored. As their lengths and musical structure are considerably different than those of normal measures, we believe their non-inclusion justified.
- The proposed polyphonic data structure allows for encoding a maximum of fourteen notes within the same time slice. If the data contains more than fourteen notes being played at the same time, the additional notes will be ignored. We believe this approximation justified due to the extreme paucity of such occurrences in the data.

3.1.4 Data Augmentation

To encourage a more general learning of Western music, data augmentation procedures are implemented before training models. Indeed, the model should learn about musical surface structure in a key-independent way and it should be able to generalise to musical segments similar to those it has seen during training except for the fact that they are in another key.

To do this, transpositions to other keys are used by shifting all notes in observations by a certain amount of semitones. When computationally feasible, full data augmentation is used and each observation is augmented twelve-fold by shifting it with every possibility from 5 semitones down to 6 semitones up, covering all possible keys within an octave range. When not computationally feasible, random data augmentations are instead done and a certain number of semitone shifting factors are randomly drawn without replacement from the set $\{-5, \dots, -1, 1, \dots, 6\}$ for each observation.

3.1.5 Summary Statistics

In total, after the application of the data preprocessing pipeline, and before considering data augmentation procedures, the dataset consists of 61 293 observations (measures),

which altogether contain 885 722 music notes.

In Figure 3.2, a histogram of pitches observed in the full dataset both before and after the use of full data augmentation is provided. The non-augmented distribution is not very smooth, which makes sense due to the popularity of certain keys over other in Western music. The full data augmentation process has the effect of smoothing the distribution, which becomes almost Gaussian-like, although it can be argued to have a somewhat triangular shape.

Figure 3.2: Histograms of MIDI pitches in the dataset. On the left, the basic non-augmented data is used. On the right, the data resulting from full data augmentation is used.

Figure 3.3 and Table 3.1, the distribution of sequence lengths in the dataset is shown. The distribution is extremely right-skewed and that only a small amount of sequences (53) have a length of more than 24 sixteenth notes; when faced with computational limits in further sections, those observations will be dropped from the dataset.

Figure 3.3: Histogram of sequence lengths (in sixteenth notes) in the dataset.

Table 3.1: Frequency table of sequence lengths (in sixteenth notes) in the dataset.

Sequence length	Frequency
4	128
6	512
8	1024
9	512
12	256
16	512
18	512
20	1024
24	64
>24	53

3.2 Model and Training

3.2.1 Preliminary Experiments

Preliminary attempts are done using a simple recurrent VAE model with flat LSTM models for both the encoder and decoder networks. In this model, a simpler encoding of music is used, which is a simple succession of *NOTE_ON*, *NOTE_OFF* and *TIMESHIFT* tokens, as described in 2.1.2. As this particular combination of a simple recurrent VAE model and naive token-based music representation has found itself some success with short musical sequences (Roberts et al. (2019)), there was hope for successfully training such a model on the dataset.

However, a strong posterior collapse problem as described in 2.2.2 was quickly observed. The KL-divergence term of the simple ELBO loss function collapses to zero as the learned posterior distribution of the latent space collapses to the prior distribution, indicating that the decoder network attempts to model the data on his own through its generative capabilities. However, the decoder’s task is to reconstruct sequences given nothing more than a musical segment’s latent embeddings and a beginning of sequence token; therefore, the attempt of the decoder model to not consider the latent code makes it have to reconstruct segments with absolutely no information about them. This causes the model to get stuck in a local minima of the loss function, where it reverts to continuously predicting the highest-scoring token sequence, which is a one-and-a-half quarter beat long middle C note (C4, MIDI pitch 60). An example of such an attempted reconstruction by this model is shown in Figure 3.4.

This preliminary experiment shows that due to the posterior collapse problem, simple recurrent VAE models are not expressive enough to successfully capture the musical characteristics of the Western classical music dataset. As mentioned in 2.2.4, researchers (Roberts et al. (2019), Wang et al. (2020b)) suggest the use of hierarchical architectures that make continuous use of the latent embedding to circumvent this problem. As their approach is also of polyphonic nature, we propose the use of a model architecture inspired from Wang et al. (2020b) for the task at hand.

3.2.2 Proposed Architecture

The proposed model architecture is strongly inspired by that of PianoTree VAE (Wang et al. (2020b)). Their model architecture can be visualized in Figure 3.5.

Ground truth sequence	Reconstructed sequence
['START',	['START',
'NOTE_ON_76',	'NOTE_ON_60',
'TIME_SHIFT_6',	'TIME_SHIFT_6',
'NOTE_OFF_76',	'NOTE_OFF_60',
'NOTE_ON_72',	'NOTE_ON_60',
'TIME_SHIFT_6',	'TIME_SHIFT_6',
'NOTE_OFF_72',	'NOTE_OFF_60',
'NOTE_ON_84',	'NOTE_ON_60',
'TIME_SHIFT_12',	'TIME_SHIFT_6',
'NOTE_OFF_84',	'NOTE_OFF_60',
'END']	'NOTE_ON_60']

Figure 3.4: Illustration of an attempted musical sequence reconstruction using a simple recurrent VAE model. On the left, the ground truth sequence; on the right, the sequence as reconstructed by the model.

The encoder model works as follows. As input, the model is fed *note tokens*, which consist of the concatenation of pitch vectors (encoded as a one-hot) and duration vectors (binary encoded) as described in 3.1.2. A shared fully connected layer encodes those note tokens into *note embeddings*. A certain number of note embeddings for each simunote or time slice are then obtained; these are fed as tokens to a *pitch-axis* bidirectional GRU encoder. For each time slice, the forward and backward hidden states of the pitch-axis GRU are concatenated, resulting in *simunote embeddings*. Finally, the simunote embeddings are fed to a *time-axis* GRU encoder; its forward and backward hidden states are concatenated, resulting in a *score embedding*, which is mapped with a fully connected layer to the final *latent embedding* z , the latent vector encoding the entire sequence.

Decoding follows a similar hierarchical structure, but from the top down. The decoder model first takes the latent embedding z as input and feeds it to a unidirectional time-axis GRU decoder, which outputs a succession of simunote embeddings, which are fed to a unidirectional pitch-axis GRU decoder which outputs a succession of note embeddings. Those note embeddings are decoded to predicted pitches by a fully connected layer, and to predicted binary-encoded durations by a simple flat RNN model. Note that the decoding process happens sequentially; decoded notes and simunotes are continuously re-encoded and fed as input to the higher-level pitch-axis and time-axis decoders.

PianoTree VAE is trained on a dataset that contains musical segments of a constant sequence length of $T = 32$ and has no native support for data characterized by varying sequence lengths, which is a characteristic of our dataset (see 3.1.5). The model architecture is then expanded upon by allowing it to pad all sequences to the maximum sequence length found in the dataset, and the loss function is adapted so as to only consider non-padded parts of each musical segment.

3.2.3 Training

The same loss function as Wang et al. (2020b) is used to train the models:

$$\ell(\phi, \theta) = CE(\mathbf{p}, \hat{\mathbf{p}}) + CE(\mathbf{d}, \hat{\mathbf{d}}) - 0.1 \cdot D_{KL}(q_\phi(z|x) || p(z)),$$

where ϕ and θ respectively denote the parameters for the encoder and decoder models, CE

Figure 3.5: Illustration of the proposed PianoTree VAE model architecture. Figure borrowed from Wang et al. (2020b).

denotes the cross-entropy loss function, \mathbf{p} and $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$ respectively denote the ground truth and reconstructed note pitches, \mathbf{d} and $\hat{\mathbf{d}}$ respectively denote the ground truth and reconstructed note durations, and D_{KL} denotes the KL-divergence as usual.

This is a simple adaptation of the usual β -VAE ELBO loss, as described in 2.2.3, to the chosen music representation. The first two terms symbolise the reconstruction loss, computed as the cross-entropy loss between actual and predicted pitches and durations, and the last term acts as a regulariser that encourages the model to learn a latent space that has a smooth Gaussian shape. This last term is given a weight of $\beta = 0.1$, which was shown to lead to good reconstruction results for music tasks by Roberts et al. (2019) and Wang et al. (2020b); the low weight on the KL-divergence induces the model to put more weight on successful reconstruction than on latent space regularisation than for vanilla VAE models. However, this loss of smoothness and gaussianity of the latent space could have detrimental effects on its interpretability.

As with PianoTree VAE, the training makes use of *scheduled sampling* as described in 2.2.2. Starting teacher forcing rates of 0.8 for the time-axis GRU encoder and decoder and 0.6 for the pitch-axis GRU encoder and decoder are used. The teacher forcing rates are slowly decreased to zero during training following an inverse sigmoid decay (Bengio et al. (2015)).

All models are trained using the ADAM optimiser (Kingma and Ba (2017)) with a starting learning rate 10^{-3} decaying at an exponential rate of $\gamma = 0.9999$ until reaching a minimum learning rate of 10^{-5} . A batch size of 128 is used and all models are trained on GPU until either observed convergence or exhaustion of maximum allocated training time. For all models, a train-validation split of 90%/10% is used and performance metrics are computed both on training data and on unseen validation data every five epochs.

Also, as mentioned in 3.1.5, the distribution of sequence lengths in the full dataset is extremely right-skewed. Since sequence lengths are approximately linearly related to sequence decoding time and therefore have a large impact on computation time, we decide to drop all observations with sequence lengths larger than $T = 24$ when training on the full dataset, resulting in dropping 53 observations.

To train models, three different subsets of the full dataset are considered to allow for comparison of reconstruction results under different data characteristics. For each data subset, a model is trained both with and without data augmentation, resulting in a total of six models:

- Models **4/4** and **4/4_aug**, trained on the entire subset of the data that is in four-four time.
 - The data subset contains 11 507 observations out of 61 293 ($\approx 19\%$ of the total dataset).
 - Sequence lengths are constant at $T = 16$.
 - **4/4_aug** is trained with full data augmentation.
- Models **ABC** and **ABC_aug**, trained only on the ABC corpus.
 - The data subset contains 15 683 observations out of 61 293 ($\approx 26\%$ of the total dataset).
 - Sequence lengths are varying and padded to $T = 24$.
 - **ABC_aug** is trained with full data augmentation.
- Models **full** and **full_aug**, trained on the entire dataset with sequences longer than $T = 24$ dropped out.
 - Sequence lengths are varying and padded to $T = 24$.
 - **full_aug** is trained with three random data augmentations per observation.

For all the model architectures, the same hyperparameters as Wang et al. (2020b) are used. These are listed in Table 3.2.

As an example, Figure 3.6 shows the evolution of all the terms of the training and validation losses as training goes on for model **full**.

Table 3.2: Hyperparameter values for all model architectures.

Hyperparameter	Value
Note embedding size	128
Simunote embedding size	512
Score embedding size	1024
Latent embedding z size	512
Encoder pitch-axis GRU hidden dimension size	256
Decoder pitch-axis GRU hidden dimension size	512
Encoder time-axis GRU hidden dimension size	512
Decoder time-axis GRU hidden dimension size	1024
Decoder duration RNN hidden dimension size	64

Figure 3.6: Evolution of training and validation losses during training for model *full*.

For the training data, all components of the reconstruction loss monotonically decrease as training goes on, indicating that the model has the capacity to learn from the data in a way that decreases reconstruction loss. As for the KL-divergence term, it increases at first as the model puts a focus on reconstruction loss and encodes data in the latent space in a less compact way. The term slowly decreases thereafter as the model learns how to encode a smoother, more Gaussian-like latent space while not sacrificing reconstruction quality.

For the validation data, a similar pattern for the KL-divergence is observed, which is expected as the gaussianity of the learnt latent space is expected to be similar whether evaluated on training or validation data. However, the reconstruction loss terms, as well as the overall loss, start slowly increasing at around 50 epochs, indicating that the model might be slightly overfitting the training data in a way that harms generalisation to unseen data, which is a common pattern in the training of machine learning models. Similar training and validation loss patterns are observed for all models. The increase in validation loss past a certain point is even more intense for models **4/4** and **ABC**, and less intense for augmented models.

Even though mostly identical model architectures and hyperparameters as [Wang et al. \(2020b\)](#) are used, the models take significantly more epochs to converge than theirs, who took around 5 epochs to do so. This confirms the intuition that our dataset is of higher musical complexity than theirs, which was expected due to the dataset's size, musical variety and use of varying sequence lengths, and due to the inherent higher musical complexity of classical music compared to pop music.

Chapter 4

Results and Discussion

4.1 Reconstruction Performance

The ability of the different models to reconstruct musical sequences is now analysed. A good reconstruction quality, especially on unseen data, would indicate that the model learns about music in a way that not simply memorizes sequences, but also understands characteristics of Western musical surface structure in a generalizable way.

The metrics used to evaluate reconstruction performance are first defined. Common classification metrics from the literature are used:

- *Precision*, which is the fraction of relevant instances among the instances retrieved by the model. It is calculated using the number of true positives (TP) and false positives (FP):

$$precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}.$$

- *Recall*, which is the fraction of relevant instances that were retrieved by the model. It is calculated using the number of true positives (TP) and false negatives (FN):

$$recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}.$$

- *F1*, which is the harmonic mean of precision and recall:

$$F1 = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{precision} + \frac{1}{recall}} = \frac{2 \cdot precision \cdot recall}{precision + recall}.$$

Since it combines both of them in one metric, it is often used as a performance metric for the overall classification performance of a model.

As per [Wang et al. \(2020b\)](#), those metrics are adapted to our particular task and precision, recall and F1 metrics are calculated on three levels:

- *Pitch and onset* level, which compares ground truth and reconstructed notes based on whether they have the same pitch and onset.
- *Duration* level, which compares ground truth and reconstructed notes based on whether they have the same duration, but only for notes whose pitch and onset are already correctly reconstructed.

- *Note level*, which compares ground truth and reconstructed notes as a whole (pitch, onset and duration), measuring the overall reconstruction quality of the model.

The use of three metrics, each on three different levels, results in nine reconstruction criteria per model. To further illustrate the metrics, two of them are explicitly defined:

- *Pitch and onset precision* measures the fraction of notes in the model’s reconstructed sequence that are present with the same pitch and onset in the ground truth sequence.
- *Note recall* measures the fraction of notes in the ground truth sequence that are present in the reconstructed sequence with the same pitch, onset and duration.

Selected reconstruction performance metrics are then provided for all models introduced in 3.2.3. Table 4.1 shows metrics for models **4/4** and **4/4_aug**, table 4.2 for models **ABC** and **ABC_aug**, and table 4.3 for models **full** and **full_aug**. Metrics of precision and recall are left out for ease of reading and focus on F1, which measures both at once; full metrics reports are available in the publicly available code. To allow fair comparison between augmented and non-augmented model performance, validation sets are not applied any form of data augmentation before computing validation metrics.

Table 4.1: Reconstruction performance metrics for models **4/4** and **4/4_aug**.

Metric	4/4		4/4_aug	
	Train	Eval	Train	Eval
Pitch and onset F1	0.9826	0.6334	0.9913	0.7941
Duration F1	0.9988	0.9486	0.9998	0.9661
Note F1	0.9814	0.6008	0.9911	0.7672

Table 4.2: Reconstruction performance metrics for models **ABC** and **ABC_aug**.

Metric	ABC		ABC_aug	
	Train	Eval	Train	Eval
Pitch and onset F1	0.9839	0.7027	0.9857	0.8796
Duration F1	0.9992	0.9604	0.9995	0.9781
Note F1	0.9832	0.6749	0.9852	0.8603

Table 4.3: Reconstruction performance metrics for models **full** and **full_aug**.

Metric	full		full_aug	
	Train	Eval	Train	Eval
Pitch and onset F1	0.9851	0.8946	0.9815	0.9402
Duration F1	0.9991	0.9841	0.9988	0.9905
Note F1	0.9843	0.8803	0.9803	0.9313

Several observations stem from the analysis of reconstruction results. First, the models all have extremely strong reconstruction performance (>0.98 F1) on training data, whether measured on the pitch and onset, duration or note levels. This confirms the intuition mentioned in 3.2.3 that the proposed model architecture is expressive enough to at least successfully memorise the large training dataset and be able to reconstruct it efficiently. In figure 4.1, selected comparisons of ground truth and reconstructed training sequences from model **full_aug** are provided.

Figure 4.1: Comparison of ground truth and reconstructed sequences randomly selected from the training dataset. All sequences are reconstructed using the **full_aug** model.

Second, validation metrics are generally lower than training ones, indicating that the model is less successful at reconstructing never-before-seen musical sequences than those it has seen during training. This behaviour is expected as models have to solely rely on their generalisation power and on their general learnt understanding of Western musical surface to reconstruct unseen sequences; whereas for sequences seen during training, they can also rely on memorisation capabilities.

Third, the validation metrics increase across models as the size of the dataset increases. For example, without data augmentation, the validation note F1 increases from 0.6008 for the $4/4$ model to 0.8803 for the **full** model. This suggests that the model’s generalisation power increases with the size of the data seen during training. In other words, the models are able to learn a more general understanding and encoding of Western classical music as they see more and more data, which strongly encourages the use of a large dataset such as the full one.

Fourth, the proposed data augmentation scheme considerably increases the model’s generalisation capability. Indeed, a large gap is seen for validation performance between similar models trained with or without data augmentation; for example, on the $4/4$ models, validation note F1 increases from 0.6008 to 0.7672 after using data augmentation during training. This relative increase of generalisation power is less important as the size of the non-augmented dataset increases. This supports the previous remark that generalisation power increases as the size of the dataset does: indeed, data augmentation is seen to be especially useful when dealing with smaller datasets such as with $4/4$, but that larger datasets already contain such a variety of music that models already have strong general learning of music capabilities and benefit less from augmentation procedures, even if they still do benefit from them.

Latent space representations stemming from the use of the $4/4_aug$ model will henceforth be analysed and interpreted. As it was trained on the entire augmented dataset and is

therefore expected to have the most general and wide-reaching understanding of musical surface structure, it is the best suited model for this purpose. It is also the model with the strongest generalisation power as measured by validation metrics, further suggesting that it has the strongest general understanding of musical surface structure out of all the models. In figure 4.2, selected comparisons of ground truth and reconstructed validation sequences from model `full_aug` are provided.

Figure 4.2: Comparison of ground truth and reconstructed sequences randomly selected from the validation dataset. All sequences are reconstructed using the `full_aug` model.

4.2 Analysis of Latent Space Representations

Latent space representations learnt from model `full_aug` are now analysed. As seen in 4.1, the model possesses strong generalisation power and can successfully reconstruct never-before-seen sequences, suggesting that it is able to encode musical surface structure in an informative and powerful way that goes beyond blindly memorising a set of sequences. Thus, analysing this model’s latent representations seems quite suitable for the goal of comparing how the structure of such a VAE learnt latent space compares to pre-established concepts of Western musical theory.

The hierarchical nature of the proposed model architecture (see Figure 3.5) makes use of several layers of embeddings (see 3.2.2). Indeed, from the bottom up, there are:

- *Note embeddings*, which encode note tokens in a 128-dimensional continuous space.
- *Simunote embeddings*, which encode all notes within a time slice in a 512-dimensional continuous space.
- Final *latent space embeddings*, which encode an entire observation in a 512-dimensional continuous space, and which are the only prior information the decoder model has access to to reconstruct sequences.

Each of these three representations will now be analysed and comparisons with pre-established Western musical theory concepts will be made when appropriate. The analysis of *score embeddings* is not considered to be of interest, as they are directly linearly mapped to latent space embeddings by a fully convolutional layer.

4.2.1 Note Embeddings

The structure of note embeddings learnt by the model is now investigated. Their high dimensionality (128 dimensions) does not allow for easy interpretation and visualisation; therefore, when appropriate, PCA is used and the first two or three principal components that encode the biggest share of the data’s variance are interpreted, as per Wang et al. (2020b). As note embeddings are directly created from note tokens, two factors of variation can be analysed: pitch and duration.

Isolating for Pitch Factor of Variation

The pitch variation factor is first isolated and the variations of note embeddings with respect to pitch is analysed. The encoder model is used to create note embeddings of all 128 possible MIDI pitches as supported by the model, as well as the BOS, EOS and PAD pitch tokens, resulting in 131 total note embeddings. To isolate for pitch variation, a constant duration of one quarter note is manually set for each note token. The resulting note embeddings after 2-D and 3-D PCA are shown in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3: PCA visualisation of note embeddings when isolating for pitch variation. All note embeddings result from note tokens with a fixed duration of a quarter beat.

The first PCA dimension, which encodes 40% of the total variance, clearly encodes pitch in an ordered way. The second dimension, which encodes 14% of the total variance, seems to represent the frequency of occurrence of pitches in the dataset. Indeed, comparing to the histogram of pitch distribution in the full dataset after the proposed data augmentation scheme shown in Figure 3.2, a similar Gaussian-like, slightly triangular shape arises. Finally, the third dimension gives EOS, BOS and PAD tokens a distinct position within the note embedding, suggesting that further layers are easily able to distinguish them from actual note pitches.

Also, pitches that are very infrequent in the dataset or even absent (MIDI pitches approximately lower than 16 or higher than 105) are bundled together in one mass in the center;

this makes sense, as the model does not see those pitches during training and cannot learn their desired placement through gradient updates. Additionally, very infrequent pitches such as the ones from 17 to 20 or from 97 to 104 seem to be on their way to attaining their theoretical placements, suggesting that they might reach it given a longer training and more gradient updates.

Isolating for Duration Factor of Variation

A similar process is now performed, but isolating for the duration factor of variation. To do so, a frequent pitch in the dataset, middle C (MIDI pitch 60), is selected, and note tokens are created with this pitch for every possible duration from 1 to 24 sixteenth notes, resulting in 24 note embeddings. Their visualisations after 2-D and 3-D PCA are shown in Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4: PCA visualisation of note embeddings when isolating for duration variation. All note embeddings result from note tokens with a fixed pitch of 60 (middle C).

The tokens are arranged according to a *fractal parallelogram*; this is explained by the binary encoding of duration used in note tokens. As those tokens are only applied linear transformations (a fully connected layer, then PCA), this binary encoding is reflected in the resulting principal components structure. In other words, each positive component in the binary encoding vector for duration will result in the same invariant translation in the note embedding space, whatever the other values in the note token are; because of this, each MIDI pitch can have 24 possible note embeddings according to duration that follow this exact same fractal parallelogram structure.

Analysing Pitch and Duration Factors of Variation Together

Both previous parts of the analysis are combined and note embeddings are now encoded for each possible combination of pitch (1 to 128) and duration (1 to 24), as well as the BOS, EOS and PAD, resulting in 3075 total note embeddings. Their visualisations after 2-D and 3-D PCA are shown in Figure 4.5.

Observations from both previous parts of the analysis still stand true, and a similar triangular structure is still present with the first dimension encoding pitch and the third one

Figure 4.5: PCA visualisation of note embeddings, both considering pitch and duration variation. All possible note embeddings are represented. The colour palette represents the pitch value.

encoding pitch frequency. Now, the second dimension is the one mostly used to encode the fractal parallelogram shape resulting from all possible 24 note durations for each pitch. Therefore, when considering both pitch and duration, pitch remains the most important factor of variance in the note embeddings, followed by duration and frequency; these dimensions respectively encode 30%, 15% and 10% of the total variance. Also, the BOS, EOS and PAD tokens are not distinguished from the others as they were in Figure 4.3; this factor of variance in the data is supposed to be relegated to later dimensions of the PCA when considering both pitch and duration variation.

4.2.2 Simunote Embeddings

Attention is now focused on *simunote* embeddings, which encode all information about notes whose onset is in a certain simunote or time slice. As a reminder, the model supports polyphonic music can encode up to fourteen notes within one simunote.

Analysis is focused on *chords* as they are associated to a significant number of high-level music theoretical concepts which can makes for interesting comparisons. Artificial simunotes containing a certain number of notes that form typical Western music chords are therefore encoded; the resulting simunote embeddings are henceforth referred to as *chord embeddings*.

As simunote embeddings are very high-dimensional (512 dimensions), 2-D and 3-D PCA is also performed when appropriate for visualisation and analysis.

Three cases are investigated:

- Chord embeddings for all *major triad chords*.
- Chord embeddings for all *chords in the scale of C major*.
- Chord embeddings for common *chord types having C as a root*.

In each case, a smaller-scale *local realisations* analysis is first performed by creating three chord embeddings per chord of interest, one for each local realisation in one of the three

most common octaves in the dataset (octaves 3, 4 and 5). Then, as per Wang et al. (2020b), a larger-scale *near-global realisations* analysis is performed where more chord embeddings are created per chord by enumerating all possible realisations of this chord within the same three octaves. This combinatorics process in the near-global realisations analysis results in 343 chord embeddings per chord for triads and 2401 chord embeddings per chord for seventh chords. For both analyses, the resulting chord embeddings are investigated after 2-D or 3-D PCA.

Analysing All Major Triads

Taking inspiration from Wang et al. (2020b), all 12 major triad chords (C major, D \flat major, ..., to B major) are first analyzed. This analysis is expected to be interesting because of the prevalence and importance of major triads in Western music, and because of the well-established music theoretical concepts linking each possible pitch of the chromatic scale together.

The PCA components resulting from the local realisations analysis are shown in Figure 4.6. The first PCA dimension, which encodes 53% of the total variance, clearly encodes the register of the chord realisation, in this case the octave in which it is played. As for the second and third dimensions, which respectively encode 10% and 9% of the total variance, they cluster major chords into four groups of *major thirds* (for example, C, E and A \flat). When going from one cluster to another in an anticlockwise motion, clusters of either *minor thirds* or *perfect fifths* arranged as the *circle of fifths* are recovered. These results evoke concepts of Western music theory, under which perfect fifths are the strongest relationship between pitches, followed by minor thirds and major thirds; similarly, the model learns to disambiguate major chords by ordering their roots spatially in the order of perfect fifths, and groups clusters of major thirds together in the first few dimensions of PCA as this is a less informative relationship for musical surface structure. These results are similar to those obtained by Wang et al. (2020b).

Figure 4.6: PCA visualisation of chord embeddings in a local scale analysis of all major triads.

The near-global realisations analysis is then performed. Visualisation of PCA components is shown in Figure 4.7. Considering a much larger amount of chord realisations is seen to muddle the clustering observed with the local realisations analysis and to result in a

tangled set of points with no strong identifiable patterns. Accordingly, the first three principal components now only explain 39% of total variance altogether, where they explained 72% of total variance in the local realisations analysis. These results contradict those obtained by Wang et al. (2020b), which uncovered the same clustering mentioned in the local realisations analysis while considering the same chord realisations explored here.

Figure 4.7: PCA visualisation of chord embeddings in a near-global scale analysis of all major triads.

The tangled nature of these embeddings suggests that using only the first few dimensions of PCA is not enough to interpret and make sense of the factors of variation of the simunote embeddings, which might be too complex for such an analysis. There are reasons believed to explain why this is the case for the near-global analysis but not for the local one. With the near-global one, the structure of the dataset leads the model to consider chord realisations from musical styles that are structurally more complex, such as multi-instrument trio sonatas or string quartets, which are absent from the simpler pop music dataset used by Wang et al. (2020b). Also, the combinatorics nature of creating chord embeddings results in considering multiple chord realisations that will never have been seen by the model during training as they are not present in the dataset. Since the model does not have perfect generalisation power, this adds noise to the data and obfuscates the interpretation of embeddings. Together, these factors bring a strong complexity to the simunote embeddings that prevents from identifying clear semantic interpretations via dimensionality reduction.

Analysing All Triads in the Scale of C Major

Next, also taking inspiration from Wang et al. (2020b), all 7 triads in the scale of C major (C major, D minor, ..., to B diminished) are analysed. This analysis is expected to be interesting because of the existence of strong musical relationships between the chords in a same scale.

PCA components resulting from the local realisations analysis are shown in Figure 4.8. Once again, the first PCA dimension clearly encodes the register of the chord realisation. Now, the second and third dimensions place each triad in a circular shape without clustering any chords together. Starting from C major and going in a counterclockwise motion, the chords are arranged in the order 1-3-5-7-2-4-6. These results are once again similar to those obtained by Wang et al. (2020b).

Figure 4.8: PCA visualisation of chord embeddings in a local scale analysis of all triads in the scale of C major.

Once again, when proceeding to the near-global realisations analysis, a tangled set of points is obtained. The reasons of this phenomenon are believed to be the same as before.

Analysing Common Chord Types Having C as a Root

We now expand on Wang et al. (2020b) by performing an additional analysis where all common chord types having C as a root (C major, minor, augmented and diminished, as well as major, minor, dominant, half-diminished, diminished and minor major sevenths) are investigated. The nature of this analysis is expected to be interesting because of the different musical functions taken on by different chord types in Western music theory. Further investigating the behaviour of seventh chords can also bring interesting insights that go beyond embeddings of triads.

PCA components resulting from the local realisations analysis are shown in Figure 4.9. Once again, the first PCA dimension clearly encodes the register of the chord realisation. The triangular structure first seen in 4.2.1 is once again recovered, with the chords in the most frequent octave (4) being slightly elevated above the less frequent ones, which stand at the same height around it.

Figure 4.9: PCA visualisation of chord embeddings in a local scale analysis of common chord types having C as a root.

The second and third dimensions form loose clusters of chord types that have interesting music-theoretical interpretations:

- Major triad (C) and major seventh (CMM7) chords are clustered together, which makes sense as they are both stable major-like chords in Western classical music that usually are not strongly pulling chord progressions in any particular direction. The augmented chord (Caug) stands close to them, which could be explained by their sharing of a major third, but it is still shifted away, which makes sense; due to their dissonance, augmented chords tend to serve unstable functions compared to major chords, such as suspending tonality.
- Minor triad (Cmin) and minor major seventh (CmM7) chords are clustered together. They are both minor-like chords that accomplish similar functions in Western classical music.
- Both dominant seventh (CMm7) and minor seventh (Cmm7) chords stand on their own. In Western classical music, these chords tend to have a strong pull towards the use of other chords; this specific purpose explains their isolation.
- Diminished triad (Cdim) and full-diminished seventh (Cfulldim7) are clustered together, and they serve similar purposes in Western music. The half-diminished seventh chord (Challdim7) stands close to them, which could be explained by their sharing of a diminished fifth, but it is still shifted away, which makes sense; in Western classical music, these chords tend to have a specific purpose of conveying heightened emotion.

Once again, when proceeding to the near-global realisations analysis, a tangled set of points is obtained. The reasons of this phenomenon are believed to be the same as before.

4.2.3 Latent Space Embeddings

The analysis of the latent space embeddings z produced by the model is now performed. These embeddings are expected to be complex to analyse and interpret for several reasons.

First, they contain all information about musical surface structure extracted by the encoder model. Indeed, since latent embeddings are the only information that the decoder model has access to to reconstruct sequences, the model learns a compact representation containing the most information possible. They are therefore expected to be information-packed in a way that contains information about not only pitches, durations and chords, as for the previous embeddings, but also the entire melodic and rhythmic structure of musical segments, resulting in a high complexity that is enhanced by the variety of musical styles in the dataset. For all these reasons, their analysis should not be straightforward.

Second, just like previous analysed embeddings, they are high-dimensional (512 dimensions); visualisation is therefore impossible and requires the use of dimensionality reduction techniques that cause an inherent loss of information.

Third, the training scheme did not enforce the use of any of the unsupervised or supervised disentanglement techniques discussed in 2.2.3 and 2.2.4. In fact, the use of the β -VAE loss function with a coefficient $\beta = 0.1$ has the opposite effect of favouring reconstruction accuracy over disentanglement of the latent space. These resulting latent embeddings are therefore expected to be strongly entangled in a way that makes it complicated to find clear semantic interpretations of single dimensions with respect to musical characteristics.

Keeping this expected complexity in mind, the latent space is analysed in three different ways. First, dimensionality reduction techniques are used to visualise the latent embeddings of the entire dataset and attempt to cluster them with respect to musical characteristics to find meaningful interpretations of the post-dimensionality reduction dimensions. Then, points in the latent space are interpolated and intermediate points along interpolation trajectories are decoded to qualitatively evaluate the smoothness of the latent space and the model’s resulting generative capabilities. Finally, dimensions of the full latent space are attempted to be directly interpreted by drawing inspiration from [Yang et al. \(2019a\)](#) and isolating pitch and rhythm dimensions.

Clustering Latent Embeddings with Respect to Musical Characteristics

Dimensionality reduction techniques are applied, namely two-dimensional PCA and t-SNE, to the latent embeddings. These two techniques have different goals. PCA ([Pearson \(1901\)](#)) finds principal components, which are orthogonal linear transformations of the original data that explain the highest possible share of its total variance. Since PCA provides dimensions that explain strong factors of variation in the data and are independent, those dimensions are expected to encode semantically important musical characteristics. In this case, PCA performed on the latent embeddings z results in the first three principal components respectively encoding only 3.5%, 2.8% and 2.3% of the total variance (8.6% altogether), confirming the intuition that the latent embeddings are of highly complex structure. As for t-SNE ([Maaten and Hinton \(2008\)](#)), they instead build a low-dimensional map of high-dimensional observations that keeps observations close together if they are similar according to some metric of distance in the high-dimensional space. Therefore, different types of insights are expected to be uncovered from PCA and from t-SNE visualisations; PCA should be more helpful to semantically interpret the latent space, and t-SNE to identify clusters of similar points.

As a first example, dimensionality-reduced embeddings are clustered with respect to music period. Resulting visualisations are shown in [Figure 4.10](#). In this case, most music period points are spread out without any significant trends or identifiable patterns. However, clusters of Baroque music are identified; this is believed to be caused by the fact that all the Baroque music in the corpus consists of trio sonatas, which are expected to share a particular musical surface structure due to the use of a certain musical style.

Figure 4.10: PCA and t-SNE visualisation of latent embeddings clustered by music era.

In [figure 4.11](#), the embeddings are clustered with respect to the average pitch of the notes

contained within the observation, which is referred to as the *register* of the observation. The first PCA component seems to clearly encode the register of the bar, allowing for a nice interpretation. This suggests that the register is the biggest factor of variation in the latent embeddings, even though it only represents around 3.5% of total variance.

Figure 4.11: PCA and t-SNE visualisation of latent embeddings clustered by average pitch of the notes in the bar.

In figure 4.12, the embeddings are clustered with respect to the average duration of the notes contained within the observation, which is a metric that is inversely proportional to rhythmic density. The second PCA dimension seems loosely correlated with rhythm density, but not in a clear-cut way, indicating that this relationship might be obfuscated by the use of a proxy variable.

Figure 4.12: PCA and t-SNE visualisation of latent embeddings clustered by average duration of the notes in the bar.

A clustering with respect to the musical key of the musical segments is also provided. If the data augmentation procedure is successful, the model is expected to have learnt about music in a key-invariant way, and no significant patterns or clusters should be identifiable. This is indeed what is observe in Figure 4.13.

Finally, Figure 4.14 provides a visualisation of the clustering of embeddings with respect to the length of the musical segment in time slice units (in this case, sixteenth notes).

Figure 4.13: PCA and t-SNE visualisation of latent embeddings clustered by key.

No patterns emerge on the PCA embeddings, suggesting that the first two principal components are not related to sequence lengths; the next two principal components are also investigated and no pattern with respect to sequence lengths is noticed. This suggests that sequence length is not one of the most informative factors of the data within the latent space, even though it was to be a very important characteristic of musical segments. For the t-SNE, some clusters emerge, but they are believed to arise due to the natural grouping of similar bars within a single piece.

Figure 4.14: PCA and t-SNE visualisation of latent embeddings clustered by length (in sixteenth notes) of the musical segment.

Other variables are also used to cluster latent embeddings, such as the corpus, the century, the musical style, the number of staves, the time signature, the number of notes in the segment, the average number of notes per simunote, the pitch range, the number of annotated chords in the segment, and the type and roman numeral of the first annotated chord. However, no identifiable clusters or patterns are identified. Analysis of further PCA dimensions also proves itself to be unsuccessful. This confirms the prior expectation for latent embeddings to be information-packed in a way that makes them hard to semantically interpret.

Decoding Interpolated Points in the Latent Space

To test the smoothness of the learned latent space and the generative abilities of the model given unseen points in the latent space, common interpolation techniques from the VAE literature are used. Two points x_1 and x_2 are randomly drawn from the training dataset and the model is used to compute their respective latent embeddings z_1 and z_2 . Spherical interpolation is then performed in the latent space between z_1 and z_2 and points are selected at equal intervals in the resulting interpolation trajectory; those interpolated points are fed to the decoder model and the resulting reconstructed musical sequences are analysed. If the learnt latent space is both informative, encodes music in a generalizable way, and is Gaussian-like, which are all desirable properties for our task, then smooth interpolations from one segment to another that are musically coherent and harmonic should be witnessed.

As mentioned in 2.2.1, spherical interpolation is used in the latent space as it is shown by White (2016) to result in more realistic results for generative models than linear interpolation. As a result, spherical interpolation has been the common approach used for such tasks in the music literature such as Roberts et al. (2019).

Examples of reconstructed musical sequences along interpolation trajectories from one point to another are provided in Figure 4.15. Interpolations are performed both for two measures of similar style and time signature (Beethoven string quartet), and for two measures of different musical style and time signature (Mozart piano sonata and Chopin mazurka). Smooth interpolations of rhythm and melody and segment length are observed from a measure to another, suggesting a smooth latent space. Qualitative hearing tests also show that interpolated segments do not sound discordant, indicating that the model is able to keep musical segments harmonic while interpolating between different keys.

This analysis suggests interesting generative capabilities for the model, as it is able to construct qualitatively realistic musical segments from never-before-seen points in the latent space.

Interpreting Latent Space Dimensions

Finally, the approach suggested by Yang et al. (2019a) is applied to identify *pitch dimensions* and *rhythm dimensions* within the full 512-dimensional latent space learnt by the model. Their approach successfully identify such dimensions important for those two musical characteristics in the latent space learnt by a MusicVAE model (Roberts et al. (2019)).

First, pitch dimensions are attempted to be identified. 2500 observations are randomly selected from the dataset and their latent embeddings z are computed. All pitches of the selected observations are then shifted up by a certain amount of semitones; the new latent embeddings z^* are computed after this pitch shifting process. The average absolute change after the application of this shifting is then computed for each dimension of the latent space between z and z^* . The process is repeated for twelve pitch shifting factors, from 1 to 12 semitones; the latent space dimensions are then ranked in decreasing order of average absolute change across pitch transpositions. The first resulting 100 dimensions are shown in Figure 4.16.

The first dimension, which is the one with the highest absolute change with respect to pitch shifting, is clearly directly correlated to the intensity of the shifting in semitones. This dimension of the latent space (dimension 184) then seems to be a clear *pitch dimension*.

Figure 4.15: Interpolation of musical segments by decoding points along spherical trajectories in the latent space. On the left, the interpolation is from one measure of a Beethoven string quartet (top) to another (bottom). On the right, the interpolation is from one measure of a Mozart piano sonata (top) to one measure of a Chopin mazurka (bottom). The interpolations are smooth and harmonic.

Figure 4.16: Latent dimensions sorted by variation level following the application of pitch transformations.

The same can be said for the subsequent five dimensions, which mostly preserve this relationship; thereafter, variations slowly become noisy and unordered, indicating a strong entanglement and no clear relationship with pitch characteristics.

Next, rhythm dimensions are attempted to be identified. The same 2 500 observations from the dataset as before are used, but now *rhythm chopping factors* are applied to them. For example, a chopping factor of 2 splits all notes within a segment into two notes of the same pitch but with a duration that is half of the original note. The highest the chopping factor, the highest the rhythmic density of the transformed observation. The same process as before is applied and latent dimensions are ranked with respect to average absolute change following the application of chopping factors. The first resulting 100 dimensions are shown in Figure 4.17.

Once again, a clear direct relationship is observed between the chopping factor and the absolute change for the first dimension, indicating the presence of a strong *rhythm dimension* in the latent space (dimension 159). This ordering is more strongly preserved than it was for rhythm, and the subsequent 20 or so dimensions also have a strong ordered effect, after which things start to become more noisy and tangled.

This analysis suggests that even though the 512-dimensional latent space learned by the model is tangled and hard to interpret, dimensions that have a clear effect on musical characteristics such as register or rhythmic density can still be identified. If those dimensions could be more efficiently identified and their effects could be more clearly understood, this would suggest a strong potential for controllable generation of music using the model.

Figure 4.17: Latent dimensions sorted by variation level following the application of rhythm transformations.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

In short, hierarchical VAE models inspired by Wang et al. (2020b) are trained on a large and varied corpus of Western classical music. By only accessing musical surface structure data, the models can successfully reconstruct musical segments and learn informative latent embeddings that efficiently encode characteristics of Western music.

Analysis of the latent representations learned by the best model uncovers the presence of characteristics analogous to those of well-established Western theory musical concepts. In particular, in some levels of the embeddings, the presence of perfect fifths and major thirds is discovered, and groupings of chord types according to their typical functions in Western classical music are observed. Semantically meaningful factors of musical variation are also identified in the observed latent embeddings, satisfying musical interpolation experiments are conducted and latent space dimensions that have clear disentangled effects on pitch or rhythm are identified. This suggests that the model, even though of theory-light structure and trained on theory-light data, successfully learns to encode Western classical music in a way that makes use of higher-level musical abstractions that go beyond observable musical surface structure.

Our work expands on previous work by training a VAE model on a Western music dataset that, by its size, polyphonia and large variety of classical music styles, has a more complicated musical structure than those usually seen in related literature (Roberts et al. (2019), Wang et al. (2020b)). Usual VAE architectures seen in the music modelling literature are also generalized to the use of varying musical sequence lengths and still obtain strong reconstruction results on both seen and unseen data. Additionally, the proposed model adds to the literature by learning a general understanding of Western classical music characteristics that has a strong potential for interpretability and for downstream musical tasks such as generation or feature learning.

We believe our work has strong potential for improvement and future work. First, the data and models could be scaled up in various ways. the models could be trained on an even bigger dataset that contains more Western music classical pieces and a larger variety of musical styles. As argued in 4.1, training on a larger and more varied dataset results in the model gaining a more general understanding of Western music that generalizes better to new segments, as measured by validation reconstruction performance; a scaling up of the dataset is therefore expected to further improve the model’s understanding of Western music. Additionally, the model could be trained on longer sequences than one bar. If model capacity allows a successful encoding of longer sequences, the latent embeddings could then

be analysed for more long-term musical concepts found in Western music theory, such as e.g. modulation, chord progressions or transitions between musical sections. The various approximation errors mentioned in 3.1.3 could also be improved upon, which would refine the quality of the preprocessed data and of the resulting models. Finally, the model’s architecture could be scaled up by increasing its number of parameters, providing it with stronger expressive power.

Second, our work could be expanded beyond the realm of Western classical music. Similar models could be trained on corpora of jazz or Western pop music and the structure of the learnt latent space could be compared in a way that provides insights into how Western musical theory concepts evolve from a genre to another. Models could also be trained on non-Western music corpora. Model structure adaptations could be required, as the use of the chromatic scale is not universal in non-Western music. The resulting latent spaces could be once again analysed for higher-level musical abstractions that would make an interesting comparison to those identified in the Western music case. Models could also be trained on a corpus containing both Western and non-Western music and the resulting latent spaces could be investigated for universal characteristics of music which could be compared to generally accepted definitions of music as a universal concept.

Third, disentanglement techniques mentioned in 2.2.3 and 2.2.4 could be used to obtain a more constrained latent space whose dimensions are more easily interpretable by the imposition of certain desired characteristics. For example, latent space dimensions could be regularized with respect to predefined musical characteristics, which could result in interesting applications for controllable music generation. However, this would come at the cost of imposing stronger inductive biases on the model, which would become less theory-light and learn about musical characteristics in a less general and unsupervised way.

Fourth, the latent space analysis could be more refined. A larger amount of the principal components resulting from latent embeddings could be investigated so as to uncover more clearly-defined semantic interpretations of latent space dimensions. More advanced techniques could also be used to interpret the latent space z , such as systematic variation of latent dimensions and qualitative analysis of resulting decoded points. As for the analysis of chord embeddings, it could be limited to chords whose occurrence in the dataset is above a certain threshold, favouring a less noisy space to interpret. Finally, a quantitative investigation into the generative capabilities of the model could be conducted by having participants rank musical characteristics of interpolated or random decoded segments, such as creativity, musicality and expressiveness.

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